
Using Workshop-Based Elicitation of Business Requirements for Co-Creation: An Integrative Approach for Capturing Tacit Knowledge

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Abstract

Well-conducted requirements engineering (RE) activities account for a significant share of success in IT projects (Wieggers and Beatty, 2013). The RE process starts with identifying business objectives that define a context for eliciting business requirements. Because RE is considered a social interaction (Serna et al., 2017), a share of knowledge about business requirements is stored as unarticulated tacit knowledge possessed by individuals within an organization (Boyer and Mili, 2011). This personalization of tacit knowledge causes barriers to gathering valid requirements (Serna et al., 2017). Moreover, intra-organization knowledge sharing is often complicated by knowledge hiding (Connelly et al., 2012), resulting from a lack of interpersonal trust between employees and (external) analysts (Holste and Fields, 2010). In Knowledge Management (KM) literature, tacit knowledge sharing is mainly discussed from the cultural and psychological perspectives (Chen et al., 2018; Holste and Fields, 2010), which are out of the control of an external business analyst. However, some publications suggested specific methods and tools that business analysts can use to foster requirements elicitation, such as creating engaging environments (Nakano et al., 2013) and utilizing social web-based tools (Panahi et al., 2016, 2013). Although a large amount of focus in KM and RE was dedicated to knowledge and requirements elicitation, we see little integration of KM-based tools and techniques in RE. Therefore, in this paper, we draw on our experience facilitating a co-creation workshop to help other facilitators effectively deal with collecting tacit knowledge about the business

requirements in organizations. We started with a systematic literature search in two areas (knowledge and requirements elicitation) and identified one review for each area that lists elicitation methods (Anwar et al., 2022; Gavrilova and Andreeva, 2012). We used conceptualization of the identified methods to design a workshop. After the workshop facilitation, we reflected on our data from participatory observation and suggested recommendations for similar workshops. We addressed several issues that emerged during the workshop, namely (i) insufficient domain knowledge before the workshop, (ii) lack of validation, and (iii) issues with capturing tacit knowledge during the workshop.

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Keywords – Requirement; knowledge; elicitation; co-creation; embedded knowledge.

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1 Introduction

Applied or experimental research, software development, policy design, and other fields use co-creation workshops as a primary “method” for requirements elicitation. Many Horizon Europe research proposals contain co-creation workshops; however, the concept of this activity is not clear nor universally understood. It can range from simple discussion or brainstorming to complex methodology. Well-conducted requirements engineering (RE) activities account for a significant share of success in IT projects (Wiegiers and Beatty, 2013). The RE process starts with identifying business objectives that define a context for eliciting business requirements. Because RE is considered a social interaction (Serna et al., 2017), even if most of the knowledge is documented, a share of knowledge about business requirements is stored as unarticulated tacit knowledge possessed by individuals within an organization (Boyer and Mili, 2011). This personalization of tacit knowledge causes barriers to gathering valid requirements (Serna et al., 2017). Moreover, intra-organization knowledge sharing is often complicated by knowledge hiding (Connelly et al., 2012), resulting from a lack of interpersonal trust between employees and (external) analysts (Holste and Fields, 2010), causing problems in project consortia where industrial partners are present.

Standard requirements-gathering techniques such as interviews, questionnaires, user observation, workshops, brainstorming, use cases, role-playing, and prototyping could increase the chances of gathering the correct

requirements (Ribeiro et al., 2014). In knowledge management (KM) literature, tacit knowledge sharing is mainly discussed from the cultural and psychological perspectives (Chen et al., 2018; Holste and Fields, 2010), which are out of the control of an external business analyst. However, some publications suggested specific methods and tools that can potentially be used by business analysts, such as creating engaging environments (Nakano et al., 2013) and utilizing social web-based tools (Panahi et al., 2016, 2013). Although KM researchers focused much on knowledge capture and sharing, we see little integration of KM-based tools and techniques in RE.

Focusing on tacit aspects of knowledge is essential when eliciting business requirements. Yet little direct attention was paid to integrating techniques, tools, and methods from the RE field into KM or vice-versa. Therefore, in this paper, we used an opportunity of working on the Horizon Europe project called DiCiM¹ and compared the typical methods from both fields. We developed a design of a co-creation workshop for business requirements elicitation, facilitated the workshop, and reflected on data from our observations to derive recommendations for facilitating similar workshops in the future.

2 Theoretical Background

Overlap between the knowledge and requirements elicitation is not very thoroughly investigated. When searching for the keywords *knowledge*, *requirements*, and *elicitation* in a title, we found only nine relevant articles on the Web of Science that focus on this matter. Our understanding of the concepts we investigated is as follows.

Requirements elicitation is a process of understanding a problem and its application domain. The requirement elicitation aims to identify as many requirements as possible to prepare several alternate solutions for the stated problem (Khan et al., 2014). Business requirements elicitation techniques provide means to discover the issues, problems, opportunities, and needs of the users by the systems analysts. After it, systems developers can design the solution to solve the issues or leverage the opportunities (Gobov and Huchenko, 2020).

Knowledge elicitation (also referred to as 'knowledge acquisition') is conceptualized as an interaction between analyst and expert, aiming to capture

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and validate the knowledge of the latter (Gavrilova and Andreeva, 2012; Schreiber et al., 1999). Primary methods such as interviews, observation, storytelling, and brainstorming (Gavrilova and Andreeva, 2012) aim at externalizing expert knowledge in the form of knowledge objects. Simultaneously, secondary methods such as cognitive mapping (Kwong and Lee, 2009) establish links between earlier elicited knowledge objects. Although both fields are very close together, requirements elicitation does not always have to cover tacit knowledge.

When knowledge needs to be elicited to identify, document, and analyze requirements, a business analyst must overcome a barrier of personalization of tacit knowledge (Serna et al., 2017). The ambiguity of elicited requirements, mainly driven by differing stakeholders' views, can cause project failure (Anwar et al., 2022). Because the tacit part of requirements consists of intuition and inspiration and depends on an individual's analytical abilities, reflections, experience, and creativity (Al-Alshaikh et al., 2020), it is crucial to make it as easy for the stakeholders as possible.

Therefore, method(s) selection for elicitation is crucial, and the choice needs to be situational (Mishra et al., 2018). For this purpose, an evaluation framework was developed (see Mishra et al., 2018). However, the framework lacks detail because it uses a shallow granular approach to categorizing the methods. It allows the business analysts to be aware of available options but does not help them to design the elicitation phase.

3 Methodology

We followed the idea of the design research (Peppers et al., 2007) methodology for designing a co-creation workshop aimed at eliciting business requirements. To achieve this purpose, we took the following steps. First, we systematically searched for literature following Tranfield et al. (2003) approach. We identified a list of methods for eliciting tacit knowledge in general and business requirements as a specific type of tacit knowledge. Second, we conceptualized and evaluated the identified techniques based on their applicability to co-creation workshops. Third, we designed and conducted the workshop. Last, we used the first phase of action research (Baskerville and WoodHarper, 1996; Mansell, 1991) to evaluate and reflect on the implementation of the workshop.

In a systematic literature search, we aimed to identify peer-reviewed literature reviews dedicated to the elicitation techniques in KM and RE. First, we queried

reviews in the KM field by using the combination of the following keywords: ("knowledge elicitation") AND ("techniq*" OR "tool*" OR "method*") AND ("review") AND ("knowledge management"). This search yielded two reviews; however, we only considered the one by Gavrilova and Andreeva (2012) after the abstract screening relevant.

The second query we applied during the literature search was focusing on elicitation techniques in the field of Requirements Engineering and thus combined the following keywords: "requirement*" AND "elicit*" as the title, and "knowledge" AND "review" as the topic. Then, during the abstract screening, we included one paper (Anwar et al., 2022) since it provided the most extensive review of the tools and techniques of requirements elicitation.

In the next step, we conceptualized elicitation techniques specified in both reviews using context-aware backward search. Subsequently, we compared the identified techniques and selected those that matched our co-creation workshop's goals. Then, aligned with the design research principles (Peffer et al., 2007), we used this knowledge to design a co-creation workshop. Subsequently, we facilitated a two days workshop in a company preceded by a site visit. The workshop aimed to elicit business requirements for a digital technology development project. The workshop consisted of three facilitators and six stakeholders, and key users. Using participatory research and observations, we reflected on the observations of the workshop on the design and drew recommendations and conclusions.

4 Design of a co-creation workshop

We started by identifying typical methods used during the elicitation. As was stated earlier, we used two review papers to establish a list of methods. For KM methods, we used Gavrilova and Andreeva's (2012) taxonomy of primary knowledge elicitation methods (see Figure 1). For RE methods, we used a review study by Anwar et al. (2022) listing RE techniques (see Table 1). A comparison between the two sets of techniques is summarized in Table 2. The rest of this section conceptualizes the techniques.

Figure 1: Taxonomy of knowledge elicitation techniques (adapted from Gavrilova and Andreeva, 2012). Notes: *May work, **Is appropriate, ***Is very suitable, - Not applicable.

Gavrilova and Andreeva's (2012) taxonomy outlines eight techniques for knowledge elicitation: (i) interview, (ii) questionnaire, (iii) observation, (iv) storytelling, (v) round table, (vi) brainstorming, (vii) role games, and (viii) verbal protocols. In addition, in their review, the authors mention the inapplicability of round tables for tacit knowledge elicitation, which puts this technique beyond the scope. Although the authors also referred to questionnaires as inapplicable, we considered them in our analysis since, unlike round tables, questionnaires can be used before the workshop to improve preparation. Moreover, the authors mention cognitive mapping as a secondary technique for tacit knowledge elicitation.

Table 1: List of requirements elicitation techniques sorted by frequency of mentioning in the literature (adapted from Anwar et al. (2022))

ID	Technique	Frequency
1	Interview - closed and open	79.31%
2	Questionnaire	72.41%
3, 4, 5, 6	Observation (including Ethnography, Social Analysis, and Active Observation)	72.41%
7, 8	Prototyping (also referred to as Joint Application Development)	68.96%
9	Brainstorming	68.96%
10	Scenarios	65.51%
11, 12, 13	Benchmarking (including Similar Systems, Requirement Reuse, and Application Analysis)	55.17%

14	Card Sorting	44.82%
15, 16	Protocol Analysis (also referred to as Think Aloud)	41.13%
17	Repository Grids	24.13%

In their review, Anwar et al. (2022) identified seventeen techniques applicable to requirements elicitation, with interviews, questionnaires, and observation being the most frequently used ones. Moreover, Anwar et al. (2022) mentioned document analysis as one of the techniques. It is worth mentioning that repository grids, the less frequently mentioned technique, was discarded in the process of conceptualization.

Table 2: Techniques for tacit knowledge and requirements elicitation

Tacit Knowledge Elicitation (Gavrilova and Andreeva, 2012)	Requirement Elicitation (Anwar et al., 2022)
Interview	Interviews – closed and open
Observation	Observation (including Ethnography, Social Analysis, and Active Observation)
Storytelling	N/A
Brainstorming	Brainstorming
Role games	Scenarios
Verbal protocols	Protocol Analysis (also referred to as Think Aloud)
N/A	Prototyping (also referred to as Joint Application Development)
N/A	Benchmarking (including Similar Systems, Requirement Reuse, and Application Analysis)
Cognitive maps (mentioned)	Card sorting

Although most of the techniques are applied in both fields, storytelling was explicitly mentioned by Gavrilova and Andreeva (2012), while prototyping, benchmarking, and document analysis were outlined only by (Anwar et al., 2022).

4.1 List of elicitation techniques

As summarized in Figure 2, with relation to the use of the techniques for a workshop, all the identified elicitation techniques can be split into three categories based on the moment when they are to be applied: (i) pre-workshop, (ii) on-workshop, and (iii) post-workshop.

Figure 2: Elicitation techniques suitable for co-creation workshop design

Pre-workshop techniques aim at collecting evidence before the workshop and helping analysts develop on-site content. These techniques include (i) document analysis, (ii) benchmark studies, and (iii) questionnaires.

Document analysis is an approach that is used to elicit business analysis information, including contextual understanding and requirements (Gobov and Huchenko, 2020; Khan et al., 2014). It examines available documents that describe the business environment or organizational settings. Document analysis may be used to gather background information to understand the context of a business need. It may include researching existing solutions to validate their current implementation. Document analysis can validate findings from other elicitation efforts, such as interviews and observations. Document analysis involves gathering information from existing documentation and could involve interaction with a human expert to confirm or add to this information (Gobov and Huchenko, 2020; Khan et al., 2014).

Benchmark studies help analysts to compare organizational practices against the market best practices. During benchmarking, similar systems or applications could be analyzed. Sometimes, benchmarking is accompanied by a market analysis that studies customers to discover the products and services they need, the determinants of their purchase decision, and the competing companies, products, or services in the market (IIBA, 2015).

Questionnaires aim at the quick collection of information from many respondents. Respondents can represent a diverse (often dispersed) population that can be easily reached and relatively cheaply (Gobov and Huchenko, 2020; Paul et al., 2014; PMI, 2017).

On-workshop techniques aim at collecting evidence on-site and involve collaboration between an analyst and, typically, multiple experts. These

techniques include (i) brainstorming, (ii) collaborative games, (iii) observation, and (iv) prototyping.

Brainstorming is a technique to quickly identify a list of ideas (e.g., a list of risks, problems, business objectives, or potential solution options). Brainstorming is conducted in a group environment and is led by a facilitator. The group generates as many ideas as possible about the topic during a brainstorming session (IIBA, 2015; PMI, 2017).

Collaborative games foster collaboration, innovation, and creativity to achieve the goal of the elicitation activity. Gameplays are used to encourage team participation and enhance engagement. It helps the participants share their knowledge and experience on a given topic, identify hidden assumptions, and explore that knowledge in ways that may not occur during regular interactions. The shared experience of the collaborative game encourages people with different perspectives on a topic to work together to understand an issue better and develop a shared model of the problem or potential solutions (IIBA, 2015; PMI, 2017).

Observation provides a direct way of collecting information about how a business process is performed by observing it in a natural practical environment (Gobov and Huchenko, 2020; IIBA, 2015; Zhang, 2007). It provides means to develop a rich understanding of the application domain by observing human activities. In addition to non-tacit requirements, some are apparent to stakeholders but challenging to verbalize. We call them tacit requirements. This technique is helpful when process owners cannot share their expertise through other models due to the lack of time or difficulties expressing ideas and working practices. In addition, this method is used to understand complex societies rather than judge how ways of working could be improved or supported (Gobov and Huchenko, 2020; IIBA, 2015; Zhang, 2007).

Prototyping elicits and validates requirements through an iterative process that creates evolutionary models or designs of requirements or is used to model user experience, evaluate design options, and as a basis for developing the final business solution (Paul et al., 2014). Prototyping is an iterative process and part of the analysis phase of the system development life cycle, which helps get feedback from the users, as users can see facilities and provide a response (Khan et al., 2014). The system analysts can evaluate the response, modify the existing requirements, and develop new ones (IIBA, 2015).

Three techniques, namely, interviews, storytelling, and verbal protocols, require one-to-one interaction between an analyst and an expert (Gavriolova and Andreeva, 2012) and, therefore, can be implemented in both phases: pre-workshop (in online format) and on-workshop.

An interview is a formal or informal approach to elicit stakeholder information. It is performed by asking prepared questions and documenting the responses. Interviews are often conducted individually between an interviewer and an interviewee but may also involve multiple interviewers and interviewees. Questions that arise during the conversation can be discussed immediately, and the requirements engineer may uncover subconscious requirements through thoughtful questions (PMI, 2017; Pohl, 2010). An interview is a dialogue between an analyst and an expert. An analyst asks an expert several questions that can either be pre-defined (in structured interviews) or emerge in the interview process (in unstructured interviews).

Storytelling is considered one of the forms of interviews, where most of the structuring is left up to an expert, while analyst just sets the direction of this structuring as in the example below (Scheibelhofer, 2008):

Could you please tell me everything that is involved in your coming to New York and how your life went on since then? I will listen and make some notes and I will not interrupt you until you have finished. Please take as much time as you feel necessary and tell me all the details you remember that, in your opinion, are connected to your living in New York.

Verbal protocols are the last interview-based methods outlined by Gavrilova and Andreeva (2012). Verbal protocols are traditionally used in social sciences as cognitive interviewing (Willis, 2005). Experts are asked to “think aloud” in cognitive interviewing and reveal their decision-making process to an analyst.

Finally, two techniques applicable for the on-workshop and post-workshop phases include: (i) cognitive mapping and (ii) card sorting.

Cognitive mapping is a technique suitable for the on-workshop and post-workshop phases. Once an expert’s knowledge is elicited, an analyst might synthesize it as cognitive maps that validate the results of knowledge elicitation with experts (Kwong and Lee, 2009). A cognitive map puts all the fragments of the elicited knowledge in one space and defines relations between them.

Card sorting is a technique used to sort various knowledge objects. Participants are asked to organize individual, unsorted items into groups. Card sorting may be conducted as a series of individual exercises, as a concurrent

activity of a small group, or as a hybrid approach where individual activity is followed by a group discussion of individual differences (Tiwari et al., 2012).

4.2 Workshop design

While designing our workshop, we had limited access to the industrial partner representatives (i.e., users of future solutions). The only pre-workshop interaction we had with stakeholders was an 80-minutes interview, where we aimed to establish an understanding of a problem domain. Afterward, the stakeholders had minimal time to validate our understanding, which decreased the “active” workshop time.

Because not a single method can solve all the problems of requirements elicitation (Mishra et al., 2018), we employed several methods in our workshop design. Since we lacked an understanding of the problem domain, we needed to start the workshop by gathering data about the processes. Therefore, we organized a site visit to observe how the processes that are part of the requirement elicitation were executed.

The next day, we needed to capture the roles and needs of the relevant stakeholders. Therefore, we used parallel sessions where each workshop facilitator did storytelling (narrative interviews) with a stakeholder. Storytelling helped us to structure the subsequent sessions.

In the next session, we combined individual and group brainstorming techniques. First, we let each stakeholder compile a list of problems that could help the company. Then, the lists were swapped with another stakeholder who reviewed them and commented on them with their thoughts. We debriefed this session by creating a cognitive map that synthesized and summarized the brainstorming session.

In the subsequent activity, we worked with the cognitive map and used group brainstorming to develop potential solutions for tackling the identified problems. Each solution was taken for detailed scrutiny. For this, we used a combination of techniques consisting of scenarios, thinking aloud, and comparison to similar systems to create further cognitive maps as session outputs.

5 Evaluation of the design

Our workshop encountered several problems that caused time management issues and lower quality of elicited requirements. The most significant problems

were: (i) insufficient domain knowledge before the workshop, (ii) lack of validation during the workshop, and (iii) issues with capturing tacit knowledge.

First, we lost a significant amount of time at the beginning of the workshop since it was dedicated to storytelling. Although storytelling sessions helped to improve facilitators' understanding of a problem domain, which they lacked due to the restrictions in the workshop preparation phase, it decreased the time available for other sessions (e.g., going deeper with individual requirements and features). Therefore, to address this issue in future workshops, we will substitute on-workshop storytelling with pre-workshop interviews.

Second, the post-workshop validation did not show to be of sufficient level. Cognitive maps are helpful for visualizations but sometimes lack explicitness and essential detail. We waited for the validation after the workshop when we finished the transcription of the sessions and developed a RE draft. Validating the document without properly validating outputs from the individual sessions was futile as stakeholders lacked time and context of the content of the RE draft. We planned short validation sessions in our agenda, but they were sacrificed due to the extended storytelling and brainstorming sessions. We did not find a solution in the literature, which mostly omits to discuss the validation of the elicited requirements. In the next workshop, we plan to divide the roles of facilitators in the way that one facilitator will focus on moderating the discussion with industrial partner representatives. At the same time, another one will, in parallel, produce outputs, which will then be taken to a discussion during validation sessions and incorporated into the workshop agenda.

Third, although we tried to employ several KE techniques, we did not successfully capture embedded knowledge. We discovered that without proper domain knowledge, it is complicated to understand all the terms and concepts that stakeholders naturally use. Studies listing and describing elicitation techniques raise the issue of complicated capture of embedded (tacit) knowledge. However, they lack practical solutions. In the next workshop, we could solve this by developing and validating the glossary of terms that could help us better understand the subtle differences in the meaning of terms and concepts unique to each organization during the pre-workshop preparations.

To summarize, we recommend that facilitators of the co-creation workshops focus on two aspects. The first is to do as much to understand a problem domain, including a glossary of commonly used terms and abbreviations in the enterprise, before the workshop. The second is to incorporate validation sessions in the

workshop agenda. These two actions are essential to improve the quality and efficiency of business requirement elicitation.

6 Conclusion

We showed that the approaches to investigate challenges posed by embedded (tacit) knowledge in requirements engineering are being tackled in different fields. However, there were few attempts to integrate knowledge from (software) requirements engineering, knowledge management, and co-creation fields. The current knowledge is fragmented and, at the same time, overlapping across the fields. We suggest that the next step could be an integrative literature review of the relevant fields to describe the overlaps and gaps in the current knowledge precisely. Such a review could answer our study's first limitation: the restricted set of techniques. Although we used two literature reviews to generate the list of techniques, a thorough critical evaluation would likely add several methods to the list. However, we wanted to see if it is possible to identify relevant methods with a relatively small effort. In an ideal situation, a systematic literature review of methods would be more suitable for generating a robust list of techniques.

Furthermore, we suggest that the practice of requirements engineering and theoretical research should be more deeply aligned as they are decoupled. Therefore, we see the solution in employing a participative methodology. Combining design and action research seems ideal to align the practice and basic research. It covers the study's second limitation caused by trying our design only in one workshop. Before submitting this paper, we had no opportunity to facilitate another workshop and use the reflection to improve the design. We will remedy this by facilitating several workshops within the same project and thus will be able to fully use the added value of the combination of design and action research.

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